

Research

The Basic Education Curriculum System in Oromia Regional State of Ethiopia: A Systematic Review of Literature

Gerba Fayera Aboma

College of Teacher Education, Department of Comparative Education, Zhejiang Normal University, Jinhua, China

Abstract The significance of education in the socio-economic development of a nation is immense. The overall social progress of a given nation mirrors the quality of education in that country. The achievement of quality education in turn necessitates a well-developed education curriculum. The curriculum plays a pivotal role in the successful journey of education. The aim of this literature review is to analyze the problems that arise from the education curriculum with regard to the quality of basic education in the Oromia region of Ethiopia. As a result, this literature review analyzed the status of the curriculum in basic education in the Oromia region of Ethiopia. Accordingly, the literature reviewed the history, development, and status of Ethiopian education and curriculum in order to recognize the clear picture of the role of curriculum in the basic education of Oromia regional state. The review of the literature reached the idea that the adoption of western curriculum in Ethiopian and other African countries without recognizing the real life experiences of society overshadowed and hampered the successful journey of education in Ethiopia in general and in the Oromia region in particular, in addition to internal problems that hijacked the quality of education. As some scholars indicate because of its roots to both Christian and Islamic education influences Ethiopian education and its curriculum focused on memorization that lack critique and rigorous that might result in fruitful result. The educational curriculum of Oromia region is also facing some problems that should be adjusted.

Keywords: Curriculum system, Curriculum development, Basic education, Oromia region, Ethiopia.

*Corresponding Author: gerbafayera2022@gmail.com

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1. Introduction

The curriculum plays a lion share in shaping the education of a given country. Accordingly, the successful journey of education is determined by more than whether a country uses a plausible curriculum or not. Whenever the country uses an organized and conducive curriculum that copes with its social fabric, it can easily create, innovate, and decimate knowledge and create a knowledge-based economy. This facilitates the overall social progress of the nation. Contrary to that, a flawed education curriculum hampers the socio-economic development of the country. Thus, the successful

journey of education is anchored on the right and advanced curriculum that indirectly determines the development of the country.

Whenever the issue of curriculum is raised, it is inevitable to discuss education since productive education is the fruitful result of a plausible education curriculum. Thus, before I directly proceed to the curriculum, I will discuss education in the context of Ethiopia in general and the Oromia region in particular.

[1] Education is a process by which a society can preserve, enrich, and transmit its accumulated knowledge, skills, and values in order to foster the well-being of its members (TGE, 1994:9). In this context, education is considered an instrument that can be used to bring about the all-rounded development of the individual and society as a whole. In addition, education is used to transform and disseminate the accepted and respected values of society to the next generation.

Education is one of the decisive instruments in an endeavor to break the vicious circle of poverty. As the objective reality in the 21st century indicates, it is education and training that liberate citizens from ignorance and acquaint them with modern civilization to 'pave the way for further development and prosperity as well. The secret behind the developed nations, or the countries that registered speedy development, further proves. This reality. Besides. Education is regarded as a human right more than a key to development and progress in developed nations. Even though education is crucial in many aspects, the introduction of modern education in Ethiopia is said to be a relatively recent phenomenon. I.e., not more than a century (1908). The expansion of educational services was found to be deficient in that it could not address the need for further access, quality, relevance, and equity problems. The status of education in Oromia is a manifestation of the overall scenario of education in the country.

Moreover. Education as a key for development as well as human rights has led to Universal Primary Education (UPE) as a focal point of interest at the international level. To actualize this interest, years have passed since countries committed themselves to universalizing primary education.

2. Literature search & selection of articles for review

The below figure indicates that the variables of this systematic literature review were the curriculum system of basic education in Ethiopia. The interrelationship among these variables is also revealed. The curriculum system of a given country highly influences education in general and basic education in particular. Accordingly, the following figures clearly depict the procedures through which the reviewer organized this literature review successfully.

Fig 1: Literature search and selection of articles for systematic review

3. Aim of the review

The aim of the literature review is to analyze the problems that arise from the education curriculum with regard to the quality of basic education in the Oromia region of Ethiopia. In order to reach a fruitful result, in this case, the overall assessment of Ethiopia's history of education and curriculum was accomplished. After relevant data and literature on the issue were gathered and analyzed, the review aimed at recommending to stakeholders how to adjust the educational curriculum of Ethiopia in general and that of the Oromia region in particular. In addition to recommending ways of making adjustments to the curriculum, the review also aimed at informing stakeholders to improve the quality of teachers, reading materials, the environment, and other obstacles that hinder the quality of education in Oromia regional state.

4. Methodology & Methods

In this particular literature review, I used a systematic literature review, locating and synthesizing primary research studies on the curriculum system of basic education in Ethiopia in general and in Oromia in particular. According to scholars, a systematic literature review has a rigorous methodology, making the review results accountable and open to criticism. In conducting this systematic literature review, I tried to employ a systematic approach to synthesizing available evidence to inform those who are stakeholders in curriculum development, basic education, and the like. In addition, since this type of review can offer a complementary mechanism for analyzing and mapping the information, it is possible to gain understanding of certain aspects of the above-mentioned variables and issues of interest. Unquestionably, I consider systematic review a useful and reliable methodology, if conducted rigorously, for delivering evidence to policymakers and practitioners in any educational setting. I determined the protocol for this particular review by adopting procedures based on the guidelines developed by different scholars. Accordingly, I evaluated the relevance of the reviewed studies and synthesized the review results of dozens of studies in the area.

4.1 Inclusion/exclusion criteria

I successfully developed inclusion criteria to determine the most pertinent studies from the initial search: (1) published between 1966 and 2022; (2) contained in the abstracts all three keywords or synonyms, as determined from an electronic

thesaurus: (a) Curriculum system; (b) Basic education; (c) Ethiopia/Oromia; (3) written in English; and (4) report original findings. A checklist based on these criteria was created to screen the studies. This review used two of the most popular electronic databases: ERIC and Academic Search Complete.

4.2 Data screening and extraction

Abstracts that successfully met all of the requirements were cross-screened repetitively with direct reference to their full papers. Accordingly, a number of articles were excluded for being secondary source studies, curriculum systems, and basic education in Ethiopia. Any discrepancy between the first two authors concerning the inclusion or exclusion of an article was then discussed and resolved. All data extraction was cross-checked by the reviewer to improve the dependability of this particular review.

4.3 Study relevance assessment

The reviewer of this systematic literature review considered nearly 39 articles in terms of their relevance to the current review's objectives. The reviewer tracked unevenly the weight of evidence, which refers to a framework for the appraisal of the quality and relevance of evidence, in order to decide the extent of relevance in determining which studies were to be retained. Consequently, five papers were excluded because of their irrelevance to the review's research questions. The remaining 34 studies were then included in the final review of the literature.

5. Findings

Regarding this particular systematic review finding, I have come up with the following findings, which fall into eight categories: (a) History of Ethiopian education; (b) Concept of Curriculum; (c) History of Education and Curriculum in Ethiopia; (d) Foundation of Curriculum in Ethiopia; (e) Curriculum System in Ethiopia; (f) Process of Curriculum Policy in Ethiopia; (g) Current Curriculum Framework in Ethiopia; and (h) Challenges of Basic Education in Ethiopia.

5.1 History of Ethiopian Education

The history of Ethiopian education begins in the third century. Modern education was introduced during the reign of Emperor Menilik II in 1908. The education system of the country in those days was meant to maintain the country's liberty and to produce trained human power through providing foreign languages (French, English, and Arabic) in order to keep up with the politics of the time (Tekeste, 1990). However, the Ethiopian education system, which continued until 1962,

- Lacks systematic and centralized curriculum;
- Since it was not based on the socio-economic reality of the country it didn't bring significant change towards development of the country (ibid, 1990) Ministry of Education and Fine Arts was established in 1942 in order to centrally manage the education system of the country. Accordingly, a major change was made to the system of education in 1963 and 1964.
- The previous 4-4-4 (structure) of education was changed to 6-2-4
- Medium of instruction in primary education was made to be Amharic.
- It was understood that the system of education was centrally organized, teachers who were brought from abroad to teach were replaced by Ethiopians; and to some extent education began to function based on socio-economic condition of the country (ibid, 1998) However, on the conference held in Addis Ababa which was organized by UNESCO in 1969 for African countries it was understood.

The review literature part of the study summarizes the concept of curriculum system types, curriculum system model, concept of basic education, historical background of basic education, types of basic education, basic education curriculum context in Africa, basic education curriculum in Ethiopia, curriculum of basic education in Oromia, and challenges.

5.2 Concept of curriculum

In one way or another, to address all these purposes of education, it is a must to think about curriculum since education is unthinkable without it. The curriculum is the central element or the main means to achieve the purposes of education. The meaning of curriculum is very illusive. To most educators, the curriculum is more explained than defined. According to Schubert (1986), curriculum can be defined in terms of "(a) content or subject matter, (b) a program of planned activities, (c) intended learning outcomes, (d) cultural reproduction, (e) discrete tasks and concepts, (f) an agenda for social reconstruction, and (g) 'currere' (interpretation of lived experience)." Once the concept of curriculum is made clear, what immediately comes to mind is curriculum development. Although the concept of curriculum development has been defined in different ways (see Ornstein and Hunkins, 2004; Print, 1993; ICDR, 1999), it is possible to put these variations into main approaches. Firstly, curriculum development is conceived as content selection (Ornstein and Hunkins, 2004).

Secondly, curriculum development is seen as the overall planning of learning opportunities (Print, 2004). And third, curriculum development is seen as the selection of contents and organizing them into learning materials (ICDR, 1999). In practice, it is possible to argue that curriculum development involves all of the three approaches. It is as much a planning process as it is both content selection and the development of curriculum materials. To this effect, in the history of Ethiopian education, anyone can impart or acquire knowledge in different ways. Those can be through the traditional education system or the modern education system. In fact, many scholars define traditional education as an indigenous and religious education system. Whereas, the religious education system in Ethiopia is further classified as church education and Quranic education (Hailegebriel, 1970). Therefore, all purposes of education can only be realized through an effective plan of education, generally referred to as the curriculum of the school system (Shiundo and Omulando, 1992; Tyler, 1949; Orestein, 2004).

Thus, it is possible to conclude that the process of development can be realized when the curriculum is designed in such a way that it reflects the needs and interests of the students and social forces existing in a given society or community. Perhaps this is why some prominent educators (Tyler, 1949; Taba, 1962) in the Institute of Curriculum Development and Research, ICDR (1999), strongly stress that curriculum issues are central to education and the curriculum should be at the heart of the educational enterprise. From the discussion made so far, curriculum is a central element or a means to achieve the purpose of education. For more educators, the curriculum is more explained than defined. In connection to these, scholars like Ornstein and Hunkins (2004), Abebe (1986), Solomon (2008), and Amareand et al. (2000) contested that curriculum is a value-laden term to the extent that its definitions are closely tied to certain value systems. Because of these facts, the term curriculum is not defined and understood to have one and universally acceptable meanings upon which all educators, educational writers, and people who are concerned about education agree.

For example, subject-centered curriculum experts such as Bestor (1963), Kroevisky and Learner (1984), and others argue that curriculum is defined as the sum total or collection of subject matters that promote the intellectual capacity of learners in the school. In connection with this, Tyler (1949) contributes much by synthesizing the various meanings of the curriculum. Thus, for Tyler (1949), the curriculum is a subject matter to be taught or a course to be given to the students so that learners bring about the desired changes in their behaviors. On the other hand, there are others who advocate an experience-centered curriculum. The advocates of the experience-centered curriculum, such as Count (1963) and Ornstein and Hunkins (2004), view curriculum as everything that transpires in the process of planning and learning in an educational institution. In supporting the above ideas, Aggrawal (2004:47) defines curriculum as everything that goes within or without the school system that is relevant to the learners, including extra-class activities, guidance, interpersonal relationships, and the like.

Derebssa (2004) and Abebe (1986) define curriculum in similar ways. For instance, Derebssa (2004) defines curriculum as all of the activities engaged in by the pupils, teachers, supervisors, principals, parents, and others that are in any way affected by studying in, though, and out of the school. There are still other scholars who consider curriculum to be a

written plan or a plan for a certain educational program. For example, Beauchamp (1982:25) believes that “a curriculum is a written plan depicting the scope and arrangement of the projected educational program for a school.” For Taba (1962), the curriculum is the plan of a certain educational program. This idea is shared by Good (1973:157) in that the curriculum is considered a plan for educational programs.

Hence, the curriculum for the above scholar is a plan or program with contents to qualify learners for a certain end. Lawton (1976) sees curriculum as something that can value culture. For him, curriculum is defined as a set of experiences designed to train children into the culture of their society. In other words, curriculum is essentially a selection from the culture of a society for the purpose of transmitting its important cultural traits and ethical systems. Still Chamber's Dictionary, cited in Shiundu and Omulando (1992:39), traces that the concept of 'curriculum' is best understood from the Latin root of the word 'currere', meaning 'to run, more probably to run a course'. Therefore, curriculum represents a course of subjects covered by students in their 'race' towards the destination, the finish line, which may be a certificate, a diploma, or a degree. To this end, having seen the definition of the curriculum from the perspective of its wider context, an examination of the documents in Ethiopia reveals that "the curriculum is an educational document of the state that is to be strictly followed by all schools and which encompasses planning a predetermined purposeful course of study for a particular target group of learners (MoE, 1993:1)."

The definition given for the curriculum in the Ethiopian context resembles the definition given by Tyler, who understood the curriculum as the educational policy in operation at the school level. Practically, it has been understood as the sum total of all subjects taught at the school (syllabus, textbooks, and teachers' guides). Even though different scholars define curriculum in different ways from their own perspectives, for this review work, Tyler's definition of the curriculum is taken as a working definition.

According to Tyler (1949:1), the curriculum is a subject matter to be taught or a course to be given to the students so that they bring about the desired changes in their behaviors. This conceptualization of the term goes beyond the notion of simply preparing a planned document to be applied later. When a curriculum document is implemented in an institution with an educational program (kindergarten, school, college, or university), interaction takes place between the document, learners, and instructors, such that modification occurs and a 'curriculum' emerges (Tyler, 1949).

To follow the procedures, there is a need for planning, organizing the activities, and programming, which is termed curriculum development. After a look at the concept of curriculum, what immediately comes to mind is the concept of curriculum development. The concept of curriculum development lends itself to different interpretations. For Ornstein and Hunkins (2004), curriculum development is the process of selecting and organizing the contents of the subjects to be taught. Print (1993) defines curriculum development as the process of planning, constructing, implementing, and evaluating learning opportunities intended to produce designed changes in the learners. For him, it must be seen as a deliberate, purposeful planning activity that seeks to achieve general and specific intentions.

The more elaborated and operational meanings of curriculum development in the context of Ethiopian educational policy, as given by MoE (1994) and ICDR (1999) in Solomon (2008:43), read: "Curriculum development is a comprehensive term that includes the collection of information, curriculum planning, developing syllabuses and other instructional materials, trying out and testing the materials, and improving the materials according to the result of the try-out evaluation and implementation of the curriculum." Although the concept of curriculum development has been defined in different ways (see Ornstein and Hunkins, 2004; Print, 1993; ICDR, 1999), it is possible to put these variations into main approaches. Firstly, curriculum development is conceived as content selection (Ornstein and Hunkins, 2004). Secondly, curriculum development is seen as the overall planning of learning opportunities (Print, 2004). And third, curriculum development is seen as the selection of contents and organizing them into learning materials (ICDR, 1999). In practice, it is possible to argue that curriculum development involves all of the three approaches. It is as much a planning process as it is both content selection and the development of curriculum materials.

Most curriculum experts believe that curriculum planning is based on objectives, curriculum (educational) experiences, which consist of content and methods, organization, and evaluation. The planning is reflected in syllabuses or subject guidelines, teacher's guides, student's texts, and supplementary materials (Ornstein and Hunkins, 2004). Some say that curriculum development does not only entail the planning aspect but also tryouts (pilot testing of the curriculum in a few classes and modifying material), implementation at the national level, and quality control. However, a look into the Ethiopian education system in general and curriculum development in particular has undergone several phases of development, and the chronological development of the system of education in Ethiopia may be debated. However, available scholarships by Tekeste Negash (1990), Teshome Wagaw (1979), Pankhurst (1974), and Woube Kassaye (2005) seem to rest on two broad historical phases: traditional education, also called pre-modern education (pre-1908), and modern education, which are further classified into different periods: from 1908–1974, 1974–1991, and post-1991 to the present.

5.3 History of education and curriculum in Ethiopia

The first period of modern education was from 1908 to 1974. This period was characterized by the formal introduction of modern or secular education into the country by the government at the turn of the twentieth century, during the reign of Emperor Minilik II. It is widely held that Minilik II had a very tough time trying to convince the general public as well as members of the clergy and the aristocracy as to the benefits of modern education for the development of the country (Seyoum, 1986). Minilik II opened the first state-supported educational institution, Minilik II School, in his palace compound for the sons of the nobility and dignitaries in Addis Ababa in 1908 (Seyoum, 1986). The aim of the introduction of modern education by Menelik II was both for the modernization of the country and to cope with the international political context (Tekeste 1990).

Furthermore, the curriculum of the government schools started by Emperor Minilik II was intended to supplement, not replace, the traditional instructions given in the church schools. The school was designed to provide a selected group of students with the linguistic and other skills necessary to enable Ethiopia to maintain satisfactory relations with other countries. Nonetheless, as stated in Woube (2005), there was no standard policy regarding curricula, textbooks, or the language of instruction. Mainly, the curriculum during this period was dominated by the study of languages like French, English, Italian, and Arabic. The curriculum during this period was known as a French-oriented curriculum (ibid. 4).

Prescriptive [curriculum] definitions provide us with what “ought” to happen, and they more often than not take the form of a plan, an intended program, or some kind of expert opinion about what needs to take place in the course of study. (Ellis, 2004, p. 4). Curriculum means the planned interaction of pupils with instructional content, materials, resources, and processes for evaluating the attainment of educational objectives. (Indian Department of Education 2020) The descriptive definitions of curriculum go beyond the prescriptive terms as they force thought about the curriculum “not merely in terms of how things ought to be... but how things are in real classrooms” (Ellis, 2004, p. 5, cited in Shaywitz and Shaywitz, 2007). Another term that could be used to define the descriptive curriculum is experience.

Curriculum is a powerful lever for changing student performance and well-being and for preparing students to thrive in and shape the future. It can help to ensure consistent levels of quality across types of education provision and age groups, contributing to a more equitable system. It can also guide and support teachers, facilitate communication between teachers and parents, and ensure continuity across different levels of education.

Curriculum can emerge from a variety of social, political, economic, and educational forces and influences at the global, national, and local levels. (Morris, P., & Adamson, B. 2010). In the past two decades or so, schools in Hong Kong have faced a change in their role and in the aims they pursue. Periods of international economic uncertainty, such as the Asian financial crisis and the global banking crisis that started in 2008, plus the local political impact of the return to Chinese sovereignty, have brought about a radical reappraisal of the aims of schooling. The future of pupils as workers

and citizens in modern Hong Kong is very different from the prospects of those educated twenty years ago. (Morris, P., & Adamson, B. 2010).

5.4 Foundation of Curriculum in Ethiopia

In Ethiopia, In Ethiopia, the notion of education has been embedded in the heart of church education (the Orthodox Church). However, according to Bekele (1991), modern schools did not develop directly from traditional institutions. This is because there was a great resistance at that time to modern education by church leaders. In Ethiopia, western modern education was introduced in 1908, though there is traditional education dating back to the entrance of Christianity in the sixth century. (Aweke Shishigu, 2015)

In church education, there is a traditional curriculum, even though they don't know whether it is a curriculum or not, that was designed for the training of priests, the preservation of culture, and the values of Christianity. Moreover, the traditional curriculum produces civil servants such as judges, governors, scribes, treasurers, and general administrators. The age of admission to a church school was fixed at seven to ten years. For many years, our modern schools followed this notion until kindergarten was introduced. (Aweke Shishigu, 2015)

Modern education was launched in Ethiopia by Emperor Menelik in 1908; the aim was to cope with western ideas and modernization and the need for innovations such as national currency, a state bank, the construction of bridges, hospitals, hotels, railroads, postal services, telephones, etc. Maheteme Selassie. (Bekeke, 1991, cited in Aweke Shishigu, 2015).

Emperors: Lij Iyasu and Teferi Mokonnen (Emperor Haile Silasie). The establishment of modern schools then spread throughout the country, and the curriculum includes subjects like science, mathematics, drawing, English, French, Arabic, physical training, and home management. (Aweke Shishigu, 2015).

The first minister of education in Ethiopia was appointed during the time of Lij Eyassu (1913–1916) (Maaza, 1966), after which the opening of a number of primary schools followed. The first curriculum guide for six years of elementary education and elementary school curriculum, which is from grade one to six, was published in 1947/48 by a committee of foreign staff (Bekeke, 1991). In this curriculum, all subjects are taught in Amharic in grades one and two.

Generally, the modern education launched in 1908 does not have another dimension other than the philosophy of church education. The notion and philosophical basis for education, which is rote memorization, has been highly manifested in modern Ethiopian schools for a long period of time. However, the contents and purpose of education depend on the political ideology of the Emperors; for instance, during the Dergue regime, they held socialist ideology with Marxism-Leninism philosophy; the purpose of education was to equip students with socialist ideology and strengthen their military arm.

5.5 Curriculum system in Ethiopia

The curriculum system is the processes, interactions, factors, and components of curriculum policy, design, and enactment. Curriculum systems are a broad concept and can be analyzed in different forms (Remillard & Heck, 2014). In order to be successful, we need answers to the questions of what, why, who, how, and when. A common strategy in large complex endeavors' is to develop frameworks that provide answers to these questions.

At various levels, such as principles, guidelines, frameworks, requirements, specifications, etc., and at various audiences, such as the community, systems, managers, operators, and recipients. One notion in relation to the curriculum is that it should be one starting point for the intended audience to engage in terms of observation leading to improvement and planning for action (management, teaching, and learning).

5.6 Process of curriculum policy

The government of Ethiopia, in its Education Policy and Implementation Strategies (MoE, Citation 2002), stated that the organization of the curriculum has been divided into two branches: general and specialized or vocational education. A general education fulfills the basic educational needs, includes all aspects of learning, and prepares the students for

pursuing subsequent specialized education. On the other hand, special or vocational education prepares the students to engage in junior, medium, or higher-level vocational education and skills. (Solomon Melese & Aschale Tadege, 2019) The Ethiopian school system consists of eight years of elementary education, divided into two cycles of four years, and four years of secondary education, divided into two stages of two years (4+4+2+2). Education is technically compulsory for all children until grade eight, but actual participation in elementary education is far from universal. Low enrollment rates, particularly in rural areas, and widespread attrition are two reasons why. According to government statistics from 2011, 20 percent of children dropped out as early as grade two, and only about 50 percent of pupils remained in school until grade eight. (M. Kebede, 2006).

5.7 Current curriculum framework in Ethiopia

In the present Ethiopian education system, the curriculum is classified into different hierarchical categories (MoE, 2009). The first cycle of primary education concentrates on functional literacy, and the second cycle focuses on preparation for secondary education. The secondary school first cycle continues subjects taken in primary school with the purpose of providing general education that will enable the students to identify their needs, interests, and potential; to enable the students to continue further education and training; and to prepare students for the world of work. The secondary school second cycle continues the natural science and social science streams with the intention of enabling the students to choose subjects or areas of training to prepare them for higher education and the world of work. (Solomon Melese & Aschale Tadege, 2019).

According to Anuwar Ahmed Gulasar (2021), the curriculum system can be classified into basic patterns or different types of curriculum, as under: child-centered curriculum, Teacher-Centered, Core, Overt, Explicit, or Written, Covert or Hidden, Integrated, Subject-Centered, Broad Field or Holistic, Activity-Centered, Null.

5.8 Basic Education in Ethiopia

According to the International Standard Classification of Education (ISCED 2011), basic education comprises primary education (the first stage of basic education) and lower secondary education (the second stage). It also covers a wide variety of non-formal and informal public and private activities intended to meet the basic learning needs of people of all ages.

According to MOE (2018), the Ethiopian school system consists of eight years of elementary education, divided into two cycles of four years, and four years of secondary education, divided into two stages of two years (4+4+2+2).

Further Ethiopian Basic Education Context BECO (1994) revealed that, in the late 20th century, far from being a fundamental human right, basic education was limited to a small number of Ethiopian urban elite. The vast majority of people—85–90% of the population—lived in rural areas where there was virtually no formal education available. Instead, children learned through their daily lives, and traditional wisdom was passed down from generation to generation. As the 20th century drew to a close, Ethiopia's educational system was in a state of crisis.

The MoE estimated the gross primary enrollment rate to be 20.5% in 1993/94, with more than 50% of students either dropping out or repeating before completing Grade 3 (Education in Ethiopia: Strengthening the Foundation for Sustainable Progress, World Bank, 2005). The problem of low enrollment and retention at the primary school level was both a result of and compounded by numerous weaknesses in the primary education system. Teachers and school directors were inadequately trained. (Claudio Zaki Dib (1987))

The curriculum was mostly irrelevant to people's lives. Teaching materials were largely unavailable. With a highly centralized education system, the public was not engaged in helping to improve education in their communities. Gender, regional, and ethnic disparities created severe inequities. For instance, traditional practices, such as early marriage arrangements for girls as young as nine years, prevented the majority of primary school-aged girls from accessing an education (Claudio Zaki Dib, 1987).

In educational literature, the study of alternative education systems often mentions “open systems,” “non-formal education,” “distance learning,” and “non-conventional studies,” among other terms. In some cases, these are employed as synonyms, whereas in others, there is no agreement as to their meanings, making it impossible to reach a consensus for their concepts. A more precise definition of such concepts is fundamental, as is their possible classification, aimed at better understanding and practical utilization. We shall therefore analyze the concepts of formal, non-formal, and informal education in an attempt to define their features, advantages, limitations, and interrelationships. (Claudio Zaki Dib, 1987).

5.9 Challenges of Basic education in Ethiopia

Since its inception, the education system in Ethiopia has faced many challenges, including opposition from Orthodox Church leaders, the influence of Western philosophy, a shortage of skilled labor, a lack of diversity, and a lack of integration of Ethiopian indigenous knowledge into the education system. Fekede Sileshi and Ketebo Abdiyo (2022).

The problems in Ethiopia's education system were that each regime criticized the previous education system rather than building on the former's strengths and developing new policies to support the expected change. However, the education system and policy governments of different regimes developed depending on the ideology they followed and the diplomatic relations they formed. Therefore, this study looks at these and other related issues of Ethiopian education problems in depth between the aforementioned epochs (Fekede Sileshi & Ketebo Abdiyo, 2022).

To sum up, the findings of the current systematic review are summarized as follows:

Based on the literature reviewed, the curriculum of the Oromia region echoed the African and Ethiopian educational curricula that faced multifaceted problems. For example, the Ethiopian curriculum is currently facing the following problems in the newly prepared draft of the Ethiopian Education Development Roadmap (2018–30).

The problem of standardization is observed in terms of the absence of developmentally appropriate curriculum and its implementation across different age groups. Because of a shortage of classrooms and trained teachers and facilitators, four, five, and six-year-old children are grouped together in a single classroom as if they are similar in their developmental needs. This merging of all children in one classroom obviously resulted in using inappropriate learning and stimulating materials for children that are not developmentally ready.

The problem of standardization is not only in terms of curriculum but also facilities, classrooms, teachers' profiles, and other indoor and outdoor play materials. Furthermore, lack of coordination among other preschool program modalities is one of the issues that needs to be addressed (Tirussew et al., 2018). Because of these pitfalls within the curriculum, they influenced the curriculum of the Oromia region and necessitated plausible remedies.

6. Data synthesis

In the present systematic review, the reviewer presented the most pertinent information and data from the included studies on a matrix with categories corresponding to different aspects of the review objectives. The reviewer went through the information under each category and solidly synthesized the results across the studies. The main goal of this cross-study synthesis was to seek common overall trends and explore potential emerging comparisons in the curriculum system of basic education on the basis of available evidence collected and documented in a systematic way.

Table 1: Countries, continents & disciplines

Countries & continents reporting findings curriculum system of basic education	Frequency	Discipline involved in studies	Frequency
Oromia	8	Curriculum	17
Ethiopia	12	Basic education	19
Somalia	7	History of education	15
Nigeria	5	Challenges of basic education	9
Tanzania	9	Curriculum framework	6
Africa	13	Elementary schools	10
Europe	7	Social & natural sciences	9
America	6	Curriculum policy	6
Southeast Asia	4	Elementary schools	5

Table 2: Types and emphases of the studies

Types	Frequency	Focus	Frequency
Curriculum development	15	Procedures of curriculum development	9
Curriculum system	9	Theory grounded system of education	6
Challenges of basic education	11	Education for all	7
Curriculum review	8	Stakeholders cooperation	5
History of education	14	Origin of education	4
Curriculum and education	18	Education for all	7
Educational philosophy	6	Philosophy behind education	4

7. Discussion and implication for practice

From the systematic review findings above, the Oromia Educational curriculum has a lot of short comings and these problems should be solved since curriculum plays pivotal role in achieving quality of education. Some problems should be solved as national level that indirectly solves the limitations of curriculum at regional level.

Though different studies have been made on Ethiopian education system, still curriculum system of basic education in secondary schools of Oromia Region is not touched. For instance, Areaya, S. (2008). Policy formulation curriculum development and implantation in Ethiopia: The book center Addis Ababa. Bekele, A. (1991). Principles of curriculum inquiry: a teaching material department of curriculum and instruction, Addis Ababa University and Solomon Melese & Aschale Tadege (2019) The Ethiopian curriculum development and implementation. All these are not address the area under study,

In most regions of Ethiopia, particularly in Oromia, start from curriculum designer to school administration has to run their part by establishing such projects in phases. However, evaluating the standards, contents and methods of existing basic education courses are found to be under questioned. As a result studying on this area may help to compare and solve problems related to formal, informal, non-formal, alternative basic education and adult education curriculum system in Ethiopia in general and in Oromia Region in particular.

There are few study conducted on the area of curriculum system of basic education in Ethiopia. Secondary school curriculum policy design, types, standards, contents and comparisons methods of existing courses are found to be malfunctioned. In Oromia region curriculum revision have been made different time however, its types, implementation standards, contents and comparisons methods of existing courses are not seen systematically. In most studied researches, still the operational part of curriculum enactment process is not touched. Therefore addressing the problem on this area will help to understand the location of instructional resources outside of the official.

8. Recommendations

Based on the literature reviewed and problems identified the curriculum of Oromia should be adjust the following pitfalls:

- ✓ To clearly understand the full picture of curriculum system of basic education, further systematic reviews should be done considering all aspects and dimensions of curriculum and basic education,
- ✓ The curriculum should be prepared in a way that understand the real life experiences of the people of Oromia,
- ✓ For the implementation of curriculum, the quality of teachers, teaching materials and other facilities should be fulfilled.
- ✓ Memorization focused style of education should be replaced by, teaching method that arose research, questions and critique.
- ✓ The knowledge adoption from other countries should be accomplished in an appropriate way.

9. Conclusion

Education plays significant role In order to achieve the overall social progress of countries. But well organized and plausible curriculum is indispensable to enhance quality of education that again contributes to socio-economic development of the nations. Because of ups and downs that history of Ethiopian education faced, the curriculum also echoed these challenging journeys. As some scholars indicate because of its roots to both Christian and Islamic education influences Ethiopian education and its curriculum focused on memorization that lack critique and rigorous that might result in fruitful result. The educational curriculum of Oromia region is also facing some problems that should be adjusted. This review also intended to achieve this task.

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Mr. Gerba Fayera Aboma

Gerba Fayera Aboma received his bachelor's degree (BSc) in Natural Resources Management from Jimma University, Jimma, Ethiopia, in 2013. He is currently serving as a master (MA) at the College of Teacher Education, Department of Comparative Education, Zhejiang Normal University, Jinhua, China.

Email: gerbafayera2022@gmail.com

